

Detrital zircon U-Pb ages in Variscan syn-orogenic deposits of NW Iberia: Relationships between sedimentation and emplacement of the Allochthon

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Flysch-type, Carboniferous syn-orogenic deposits were laid down in relation to the emplacement of a large allochthonous nappe stack in the Variscan belt of NW Iberia. New LA-ICP-MS U-Pb age populations of detrital zircons are considered together with previously dated samples (Martínez Catalán *et al.*, 2004, 2008) to establish the relationships between thrusting and sedimentation. The age populations of four syn-orogenic formations (Gimonde, San Vitero, Almendra and San Clodio), are compared with those of the pre-orogenic sequence in the Autochthon and Parautochthon, representing the Gondwana passive margin, and in the Allochthon, formed by peri-Gondwanan and oceanic terranes.

Furthermore, a new structural study has been carried out to understand the relationships between the syn-orogenic deposits and the development of Variscan structures. The aims are to identify the sources of sediments and to establish the relationship between Variscan structural evolution and syn-orogenic sedimentation.

The zircon age populations point to the Allochthon as the main source of detritus for the syn-orogenic basins, as shown by the scarcity of Mesoproterozoic zircons, the relative abundance of Paleozoic, pre-Variscan zircons, and the presence of early-Variscan and Variscan zircons in the syn-orogenic sediments. A limited participation of the Parautochthon and Autochthon in the younger formations is possible, as indicated by relatively young Variscan zircons.

The more internal syn-orogenic formations underlie the Allochthon and are pervasively imbricated in thrust sheets with the pre-orogenic Parautochthon. However, the more external of the studied formations, San Clodio, lies unconformably upon from the reverse limb of a previously developed recumbent fold, and is weakly affected by thrusting. This indicates erosion pre-dating syn-orogenic sedimentation at the front of the nappe stack, which can be explained by the development of a forebulge outwards from the allochthonous front, and of depocenters that hosted the syn-orogenic sedimentation.

Together with the trend shown by the more recent zircons in each formation, that are younger towards the external zones, the data suggest that sedimentation occurred in progressively migrating depocenters formed in front of the allochthonous wedge during its emplacement.

References

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